

Bank Danamon Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics around Bank Danamon using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Bank Danamon " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Bank Danamon based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 6 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Bank Danamon Syariah and Conventional, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Bank Danamon Syariah; and (6) Other issues. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Danamon, both frequently and rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Bank Danamon Sharia and Conventional; Library Research

Introduction

Sharia financial operational system developed based on the holy book Al-Qur'an and the hadith of the Prophet Muhammad Shallallahu 'Alaihi Wasallam, and applies the principles of Islamic muamalah. Sharia finance is present as an alternative solution to the problem of usurious bank interest (Karim, 2004). Sharia banks are banks that operate without relying on interest rates (Muhammad, 2004). PT Bank Danamon Syariah is a company active in the banking services sector. One of its duties is to serve certain parties or the general public who wish to make savings or financing transactions using the principles of Islamic law.

Bank Danamon is a company that operates in the field of financial institutions or financial services where one of the most important factors is the ability to provide integrated customer service. In providing good quality service to customers, Bank Danamon has a responsive attitude to every complaint and complaint from customers, apart from that the company pays more attention to speed, accuracy and providing complete and accurate information about the products it has (Siangka & Hajjad, 2021).

Scientific publications about Bank Danamon Syariah are very minimal. Based on searches via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). From the searches obtained from 2011 to 2020, there were only 4 studies for Bank Danamon Syariah, while for Bank Danamon Indonesia from 2004 to 2022 there

were 134 studies. This shows that Bank Danamon Syariah's research is still very small.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Bank Danamon use library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Bank Danamon, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Danamon, both frequently and rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Bank Danamon Indonesia Tbk is a company that provides services in the banking sector, founded in Indonesia on July 16 1956. Initially, Bank Danamon was called Bank Kopra Indonesia, then in 1976 it changed its name to Bank Danamon Indonesia. On its official website, Bank Danamon provides information regarding its corporate actions from 2013 to 2020 (Disya Angger, Naufal Rafif, and Suparna Wijaya, 2022). Bank Danamon Syariah is a company involved in the service aspect. Bank Danamon Syariah has a mission, namely to serve the community by carrying out financial savings financing transactions at Bank Danamon Syariah offices. In terms of serving the general public, especially Indonesia, every employee must be friendly towards customers who visit the bank. (Syarif, M. Yasin, and M. Kamal, 2020). PT Bank Danamon Indonesia is a company operating in the business sector, namely banking, which has good performance demonstrated through high work performance (M. Tony., Lie, D., Butarbutar, M., & Inrawan, A. 2015).

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The research object is Bank Danamon Syariah and Conventional. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Bank Danamon Syariah and Conventional. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Bank Danamon Syariah and Conventional " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been

collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Danamon Syariah and Conventional Banks based on the journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Danamon's Financial Performance

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 17 topics related to Bank Danamon's financial performance, namely:

1. First, the effect of divestment information on stock prices.
2. Second, the effect of mergers on financial performance and profitability.
3. Third, the influence of the volume of credit on income levels.
4. Fourth, the influence of financial reports on the level of liquidity.
5. Fifth, measuring the level of bank health using the Risk Based Bank Rating, RGEC and CAMEL methods.
6. Sixth, funding policy.
7. Seventh, the influence of consumer credit distribution on credit interest income.
8. Eighth, the influence of Corporate Social Responsibility / CSR on company image.
9. Ninth, the influence of Debt to Equity Ratio /DER and Cash Conversion Cycle on stock returns.
10. Tenth, the effect of mergers, Market Value Added/ MVA, Financial Value Added/ FVA, liquidity risk, profitability ratio, Cash Ratio, Loan to Deposit Ratio/ LDR, Gross Profit Margin/ GPM, Return On Equity/ ROE, and capital to performance ratio finance.
11. Eleventh, the effect of the acquisition on the valuation of the fair market value of shares.
12. Twelfth, Degree of Financial Leverage.
13. Thirteenth, the influence of cash turnover, receivables turnover, Corporate Social Responsibility /CSR on profitability.
14. Fourteenth, the influence of asset structure, asset growth and profitability on capital structure.
15. Fifteenth, the influence of Return On Assets /ROA and Return On Equity /ROE on the Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR.
16. Sixteenth, the influence of Return On Assets /ROA and Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR on Non-Performing Loans/ NPL.
17. Seventeenth, the influence of Loan to Deposit Ratio / LDR, inflation and BI interest rates on Return On Assets / ROA.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Danamon Employee Performance

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 30 topics related to the performance of Bank Danamon employees, namely:

1. Workload;
2. Organizational culture/climate;
3. Discipline;
4. business ethics;
5. Credit card facilities;
6. Transformational leadership style;
7. Gender;

8. Good Corporate Governance /GCG;
9. Intensive;
10. Emotional intelligence;
11. Personality;
12. Competence;
13. Communication;
14. Compensation;
15. Competence;
16. Technological literacy;
17. Motivation;
18. Job transfer;
19. Employee placement;
20. Division of work;
21. Training;
22. Fashionable appearance;
23. Knowledge;
24. Job promotion;
25. Work procedures;
26. Achievement assessment;
27. Recruitment;
28. HR management information system;
29. Job stress;
30. Overtime working time.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Danamon Customer Behavior

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 18 topics related to Bank Danamon customer behavior, namely:

1. Accessibility;
2. Cost;
3. Brand experience;
4. Brand image;
5. Customer value;
6. Company image;
7. Digital banking;
8. Security;
9. Trust;
10. Service quality;
11. Product quality;
12. Personal selling;
13. Customer service / CS;
14. Promotion;
15. Rewards;
16. Interest rate;
17. Marketing strategy;
18. Word of mouth marketing on interest in applying for credit.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Danamon Bank Financing/Credit Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 10 research topics related to Bank Danamon financing products, namely:

1. First, the influence of market credit on the development of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs).
2. Second, the decision on the feasibility of granting credit uses the AHP and Weighted Product methods.
3. Third, the heir's responsibility for the heir's credit debt.
4. Fourth, the influence of financial performance, liquidity ratios, solvency and profitability on lending.
5. Fifth, resolving bad/problematic credit.
6. Sixth, guarantee/collateral in financing, in the form of a permit to use the business premises and inventory items (stock of merchandise).
7. Seventh, the use of cession institutions in kiosk collateral credit agreements.
8. Eighth, the use of debt collectors in resolving bad credit cards.
9. Ninth, financing without collateral/guarantee.
10. Tenth, the function of insurance in financing.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Danamon Syariah

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 5 research topics related to Bank Danamon Syariah, namely:

1. First, determine the form of sharia business.
2. Second, the role of managers in managing Mudharabah financing.
3. Third, the influence of Quality of Work Life /QWL on employee performance.
4. Fourth, the application of the Musyarakah Mutanaqisah agreement to Home Ownership Credit/KPR financing.
5. Fifth, the application of ta'zir to the financing of Ijarah Al Muntahiya Bit Tamlik/IMBT.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Other Issues at Bank Danamon

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 9 research topics related to issues at Bank Danamon, namely:

1. First, the legal aspect of foreign share ownership with the enactment of Bank Indonesia Regulation no. 14/8/PBI/2012.
2. Second, the influence of accounting responsibility on management achievement assessments.
3. Third, implementing a bank guarantee.
4. Fourth, the implementation of the execution auction through KPKNL.
5. Fifth, the ICBS/ Integrated Computerized Banking System banking information system.
6. Sixth, fast-fourier transformation modeling on corporate bond valuation.
7. Seventh, the application of the Altman Z-Score in predicting company bankruptcy.
8. Eighth, analysis of information technology investment.
9. Ninth, corporate action taxation.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 6 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Bank Danamon Syariah and Conventional, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2)

Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Bank Danamon Syariah; and (6) Other issues.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. *Kompetensi (Competence : Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>

- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>